

Supporting Information:

How Microscale Flow and Vapor Transport Shape New Particle Formation and Growth

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S1 Full Governing Equations for Air3D

Air3D is a three-dimensional extension of the two-dimensional CFD–aerosol dynamics model developed in Ghosh et al.^{S1}. It solves the conservation equations for mass, momentum, energy, and species, using a finite-volume approach with a buoyancy-modified standard $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence closure scheme. The governing equations are:

- **Mass conservation (continuity):**

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}}_{\text{local density change}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho u_i)}_{\text{advective transport}} = 0 \quad (\text{S1.1})$$

where ρ is the air density, t is time, $x_i \in \{x, y, z\}$ denotes spatial direction, and u_i is the velocity component in the x_i direction. The first term represents the local change

in density with time, and the second term accounts for the divergence of mass due to advection.

- **Momentum conservation (including buoyancy):**

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underbrace{\frac{\partial(\rho u_i)}{\partial t}}_{\text{local change in momentum}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho u_i u_j)}_{\text{convective transport}} \\
= & \underbrace{-\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i}}_{\text{pressure gradient}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu_{\text{eff}} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right]}_{\text{viscous stress}} + \underbrace{\rho g_i}_{\text{buoyancy}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S1.2}$$

where P is pressure, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = \mu + \mu_t$ is the effective dynamic viscosity (molecular μ combined with turbulent μ_t), and g_i is the component of gravitational acceleration. Each term represents forces per unit volume acting on a fluid parcel.

- **Energy conservation:**

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underbrace{\frac{\partial(\rho T)}{\partial t}}_{\text{local temperature change}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho u_i T)}_{\text{advective heat transport}} \\
= & \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\frac{\mu}{\text{Pr}} + \frac{\mu_t}{\text{Pr}_t} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right]}_{\text{thermal diffusion}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial Q_{\text{th}}}{\partial t}}_{\text{thermal source}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S1.3}$$

where T is temperature, Pr and Pr_t are molecular and turbulent Prandtl numbers, respectively. In this study, we assume that emissions are at ambient temperature and do not contribute additional heat; hence, the change in thermal energy with time $\frac{\partial Q_{\text{th}}}{\partial t} = 0$.

- **Species transport:**

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underbrace{\frac{\partial(\rho C)}{\partial t}}_{\text{local concentration change}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho u_i C)}_{\text{advective transport}} \\
 &= \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\frac{\mu}{Sc} + \frac{\mu_t}{Sc_t} \right) \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_i} \right]}_{\text{diffusion (molecular + turbulent)}} + \underbrace{S_C}_{\text{source}} - \underbrace{4J_{A4B4}}_{\text{nucleation sink}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{S1.4}$$

where C is the vapor concentration, Sc and Sc_t are the molecular and turbulent Schmidt numbers, S_C is the source term representing emissions or chemical production of the species, and J_{A4B4} is the nucleation rate (described in Section S2, Eq. S2.2) used here to represent loss of species to the nucleation process.

Air3D provides dynamically evolving 3D fields of temperature, humidity, velocity, and pressure to AMChem at each time step. These fields modulate nucleation, condensation, and gas–particle chemistry. Updated vapor fields from AMChem feed back into the species transport equation in Air3D. Coupling is performed using a fully implicit scheme to maintain stability under sharp gradients.

S2 Full Governing Equations for AMChem

The AMChem module simulates aerosol dynamics through nucleation, coagulation, condensation, and deposition using a sectional representation of particle sizes. The general dynamic equation for the number concentration $N(V, x_i, t)$ of particles with volume V , at spatial location $x_i \in \{x, y, z\}$ and time t , is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial N(V, x_i, t)}{\partial t} = & \underbrace{J_{A_4B_4}(x_i, t) \delta(V - V_{\text{crit}})}_{\text{nucleation}} \\
& + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \int_0^V K_g(V', V - V') N(V', x_i, t) N(V - V', x_i, t) dV'}_{\text{coagulation production}} \\
& - \underbrace{N(V, x_i, t) \int_0^\infty K_g(V, V') N(V', x_i, t) dV'}_{\text{coagulation loss}} \\
& - \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial V} [C(V, x_i, t) N(V, x_i, t)]}_{\text{condensational growth}} \\
& - \underbrace{k(V, x_i, t) N(V, x_i, t)}_{\text{deposition loss}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S2.1}$$

Each term in Equation S2.1 represents a physical process:

- **Nucleation term:**

This term describes the formation of stable clusters from gas-phase precursors, implemented using the cluster-kinetic formulation from Brean et al.^{S2}. The nucleation rate of four-acid–four-base clusters is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{A_4B_4} = & \frac{\beta_{A_1B_1}^3}{2 (CS + \beta_{A_1B_1} [H_2SO_4])^2} [H_2SO_4]^4 \eta^4 \\
& \times \left[1 + 2 \frac{\gamma + CS}{\beta_{A_1B_1} [B] + CS} \right] \\
& \times \left[1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + 2 \frac{\gamma + CS}{\beta_{A_1B_1} [B] + CS} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{S2.2}$$

where, $[H_2SO_4]$ and $[B]$ represent the gas-phase concentrations of sulfuric acid and a base species (such as DMA, MEA, or NH_3). The parameter $\beta_{A_1B_1}$ denotes the collision rate of acid–base dimers, while γ is the evaporation rate of intermediate molecular clusters. The term CS represents the condensation sink, accounting for vapor losses to

pre-existing particles (see supporting information in Brean et al.^{S2}). Finally, η is the cluster formation efficiency, reflecting the kinetic probability that colliding acid–base molecules proceed to form a stable cluster.

- **Coagulation terms:**

These terms represent particle–particle collisions across five different coagulation pathways. The first integral corresponds to the gain of particles of volume V from collisions of smaller particles, while the second represents the loss of particles of volume V due to collisions with other particles of volume V' . In this study, we include the Brownian coagulation kernel ($b_{V,V'}^B$), which accounts for Brownian motion–driven collisions with transition-regime corrections; the convective Brownian diffusion enhancement kernel ($b_{V,V'}^{DE}$), which incorporates enhancement of Brownian coagulation by convective motion; the gravitational collection kernel ($b_{V,V'}^{GC}$), representing collisions due to differences in terminal settling velocities including collision efficiency effects; the turbulent inertial motion kernel ($b_{V,V'}^{TI}$), describing coagulation from inertial impaction in turbulent flows; and the turbulent shear kernel ($b_{V,V'}^{TS}$), which accounts for shear-induced collisions in turbulent flow. All kernels are implemented following the formulations in Vohra et al.^{S3}, which include slip-flow corrections and Van der Waals interactions where applicable. The total coagulation kernel is then given by

$$K_g(V, V') = b_{V,V'}^B + b_{V,V'}^{DE} + b_{V,V'}^{GC} + b_{V,V'}^{TI} + b_{V,V'}^{TS}. \quad (\text{S2.3})$$

- **Condensational growth term:**

The growth rate due to condensation of vapor onto particle surfaces is modeled using a modified form of the expression from Laakso et al.^{S4}, excluding enhancement factor and charge. The condensational growth rate is:

$$C_{\text{cond}} = C_V N_V c_b, \quad (\text{S2.4})$$

where N_V is the particle number concentration in each size bin of volume V , c_b is the concentration of the condensing vapor (in this case H_2SO_4), and C_V is the condensation coefficient.

- **Deposition term:**

This term accounts for the removal of particles to surfaces (ground), with deposition rate $k(V, x_i, t)$ defined as in Vohra et al.^{S3} and Ghosh et al.^{S1}, incorporating gravitational settling, surface interaction, and size-dependent deposition velocities in the model domain.

All terms in AMChem are resolved at each time step using an semi-implicit numerical scheme to maintain stability and conserve mass and number as described in Ghosh et al.^{S5}. The module receives updated environmental fields (temperature, RH, vapor concentrations) from Air3D and passes aerosol size distributions to Aero3D for 3D particle transport.

S3 Full Governing Equations for Aero3D

The Aero3D module tracks the evolution of the aerosol number concentration $N(V, x_i, t)$ as a function of particle volume V , spatial position $x_i \in \{x, y, z\}$, and time t . Transport occurs by advection and turbulent diffusion using flow and turbulence fields provided by Air3D.

The size-resolved transport equation, derived from the general dynamic equation in Ghosh et al.^{S1}, is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N(V, x_i, t)}{\partial t} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} [u_i(x_i, t) N(V, x_i, t)]}_{\text{advection}} \\ = \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[D_{\text{eff}}(V, x_i, t) \frac{\partial N(V, x_i, t)}{\partial x_i} \right]}_{\text{turbulent + Brownian diffusion}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.1})$$

Here, the term $\partial N/\partial t$ represents the local rate of change in aerosol number concentration. The velocity component $u_i(x_i, t)$ is the airflow in the x_i direction, obtained directly

from Air3D. The effective diffusivity $D_{\text{eff}}(V, x_i, t)$ combines Brownian diffusion, D_B , and turbulence-induced eddy diffusivity, D_t , such that

$$D_{\text{eff}} = D_B + D_t.$$

Brownian diffusion is computed using the Stokes–Einstein relation, while eddy diffusivity is derived from local turbulence intensity resolved by Air3D.

Aero3D operates on the size-resolved aerosol populations produced by AMChem at each time step and evolves them through the domain using the resolved flow and mixing fields. This allows explicit representation of spatial gradients and heterogeneity in aerosol evolution, features that cannot be captured by traditional 0D box models such as Brean et al.^{S2}, which assume a spatially homogeneous particle field.

S4 Input parameters

(a)

(b)

Figure S4.1: Chemical input parameters used in the simulations: (a) Diurnal variation of sulfuric acid concentration, peaking at noon with a maximum concentration of $5 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, representing photochemically driven production under clear-sky conditions; (b) Nucleation rates (J) as a function of sulfuric acid concentration for the three bases: dimethylamine (DMA), monoethanolamine (MEA), and ammonia (NH_3)^{S2}.

(a)

(b)

Figure S4.2: Meteorological input parameters used in the simulations, based on measurements reported in:^{S6} (a) Diurnal cycle of temperature (blue, left axis) and relative humidity (orange, right axis), representing typical summertime urban conditions; (b) Wind rose diagram showing the distribution of wind direction and speed for the 24-hour period, with prevailing winds from the west and southwest and speeds mostly below 1 m s^{-1} .

S5 Additional results

S5.1 Spatio-temporal evolution of N_{1-10}

Figure S5.1: Spatio-temporal evolution of the total number concentration of particles sized 1 – 10 nm, denoted by N_{1-10} (in m^{-3}), at four time points from the start of simulation: (a) 6 hours, (b) 12 hours, (c) 18 hours, and (d) 24 hours. Each row corresponds to a different initial emission geometry case: (i) point source (PS), (ii) line source with 200 m side length (LS200), (iii) line source with 300 m side length (LS300), and (iv) line source with 500 m side length (LS500).

S5.2 Growth rates

Figure S5.2: Three-dimensional distribution of particle growth rate in the 1–3 nm size range (denoted GR_{1-3}), evaluated over the duration of NPF events within the 24-hour simulation period, under four different emission geometry cases: (a) point source (PS); line sources with (b) 200 m side length (LS200), (c) 300 m side length (LS300), and (d) 500 m side length (LS500). GR_{1-3} reflects the earliest stage of growth immediately following nucleation. Growth in this range is generally weak (typically $< 5 \text{ nm hr}^{-1}$) and spatially intermittent, highlighting the importance of localized vapor enrichment for particle survival.

Figure S5.3: Three-dimensional distribution of particle growth rate in the 3–10 nm size range (denoted GR_{3-10}), evaluated over the duration of NPF events within the 24-hour simulation period, under four different emission geometry cases: (a) point source (PS); line sources with (b) 200 m side length (LS200), (c) 300 m side length (LS300), and (d) 500 m side length (LS500). GR_{3-10} corresponds to an intermediate stage where particles grow beyond the nucleation mode. Spatial structure is more organized compared to GR_{1-3} , though peak growth rates still rarely exceed 10 nm hr^{-1} .

Figure S5.4: Three-dimensional distribution of particle growth rate in the 10–25 nm size range (denoted GR_{10-25}), evaluated over the duration of NPF events within the 24-hour simulation period, under four different emission geometry cases: (a) point source (PS); line sources with (b) 200 m side length (LS200), (c) 300 m side length (LS300), and (d) 500 m side length (LS500). GR_{10-25} captures the transition toward the Aitken mode. Growth in this regime is more spatially uniform and efficient, with rates often exceeding 30 nm hr^{-1} , indicating more robust vapor availability and reduced loss.

Table S5.1: Absolute percentage error in particle growth rates (GR) for each 3D emission scenario relative to the 0D reference, computed as $\frac{|GR_{3D} - GR_{0D}|}{GR_{0D}} \times 100\%$, for the three size ranges defined in Fig. 8. Also shown are the RMSE values (nm hr^{-1}) and corresponding percentage RMSE for each size range.

Size range	PS (%)	LS200 (%)	LS300 (%)	LS500 (%)	RMSE (nm hr^{-1})	%RMSE
a (3–10 nm)	92.22	7.61	53.47	–	0.0750	7.50
b (10–25 nm)	40.63	12.93	6.66	50.64	0.0388	3.88
c (25–40 nm)	244.72	610.78	739.70	287.03	0.3760	37.60

References

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